

Political conocimiento in teaching mathematics: Intersectional identities as springboards and roadblocks

Rochelle Gutiérrez, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, ✉ rg1@illinois.edu

Marrielle Myers, Kennesaw State University

Kari Kokka, University of Pittsburgh

Today's mathematics teachers must navigate the politics of teaching and learning mathematics in various contexts. Yet, many teacher preparation programs continue to focus on content and pedagogical knowledge, leaving teachers unprepared for these challenges. This study investigates the role of intersectional identities on the ways 49 teacher candidates (TCs) in the United States engaged with a tool designed to develop their abilities to analyze school politics to develop their propensities to intervene on behalf of historically marginalized students. Findings indicate TCs' racialized identities, personalities, ethical positions, and grade levels impacted the ways they were (or were not) compelled to act. Implications for future research are discussed.

Introduction

All teachers face politics in their work lives. Yet, teachers of mathematics are uniquely challenged by a subject that is the focus of high stakes tests and which many believe to be neutral, culture-free, and universal. Rather than believing they will develop this political knowledge “on-the-job,” teacher candidates (TCs) need opportunities to critically analyze school policies (e.g., placement of students into courses, state/district mandates) and administrator and colleague actions (e.g., adopting textbooks that are difficult for multilingual students; enforcing pacing guides) to recognize injustices and advocate for students. This aligns with professional standards in the field, such as the Association of Mathematics Teacher Educators' Standards for Teaching Mathematics (AMTE, 2017).

Teacher identities are deeply connected to the kinds of actions they carry out in teaching (Holland et al., 2003) and are shaped by professional experiences and demands (Aguirre, Mayfield-Ingram, & Martin, 2013), as well as the communities in which they participate (Gonzalez, 2009). As such, we have argued that developing political conocimiento with TCs is not a universal activity that can be inserted into a methods course without careful consideration of other work in that program/course, the teacher educator's intersectional identity and what their goals are, who the teachers are, and the nature of their work contexts (Myers, Kokka, & Gutiérrez, 2021). In this paper, we offer empirical results from the point of view of three womxn scholars of Color and our teacher candidates who range in intersectional identities, but who are primarily white womxn. In particular, we focus on our use

Please cite as: Gutiérrez, R., Myers, M., & Kokka, K. (2021). Political conocimiento in teaching mathematics: Intersectional identities as springboards and roadblocks. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 2, pp. 507–516). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5414228>

of one tool, The Difficulty Sort, which asks teachers to categorize how difficult a particular political scenario might be for them to respond to. We highlight the ways in which TC's intersectional identities influence the meanings they make and the actions they envision. We argue for the continued need to focus on TC identities and contexts, which helps counter the tendency of a methods fetish in education.

Political conocimiento in teaching mathematics

Political Conocimiento in Teaching Mathematics (PCTM) is a theoretical lens that highlights the political knowledge mathematics teachers need to navigate their practice (Gutiérrez, 2012). To date, research on the politics of mathematics teaching has primarily focused on calls for programs to develop teachers' political knowledge (AMTE, 2017; Gutiérrez, 2013) or the strategies that teachers have used to enact ethical practice (Brown, 2017). The field still knows little about the specific meanings that TCs make while they are developing such political knowledge, though noted exceptions include Gutiérrez, (2015) and Gutiérrez & Gregson (2014). Several questions arise, such as: Given the salience of race in the US, what is the meaning that teachers of Color versus teachers who are white make of these activities? Do teachers who focus on early grades (e.g., elementary) engage with these activities differently than teachers who teach middle/high school students? And, to what extent should the activities be designed to reflect the backgrounds and teaching contexts of TCs? Another limitation of PCTM research has been the focus on "rehearsals" (Gutiérrez, Gerardo, Vargas, 2017) that require significant time and the ability to facilitate a theater-like performance on-the-spot. More nimble and transitional tools are required if we expect to expand efforts. Our work seeks to fill this void in the field and answer some of the aforementioned questions by presenting empirical results from such activities with TCs in different contexts and over a range of grade levels.

Context/data

This study is a cross-case analysis of three teacher education sites in the United States (East coast, Southeast, and Midwest) that differ in several ways (e.g., grade level focus, intersectional identities of teacher candidates, program structure and focus on anti-racism/justice, types of school placements for observation and student teaching, etc.). In the larger project, we seek to understand how TCs make sense of activities that support them to develop political conocimiento, so as to further theorize PCTM and offer the field a set of tools to use with other TCs.

During the 2020-2021 academic year, after obtaining signed consent forms from participants, each of us carried out several activities with our teacher candidates in mathematics methods courses we taught via Zoom. We used four Political Conocimiento Development Tools we created to support them to develop the knowledge and ability to advocate for historically minoritized/oppressed students. These tools are: How Would You Classify It?, Difficulty Sort, Similarity Sort, and Mapping/Rehearsal (see Figure 1). All sessions using these tools were video recorded then transcribed by research team members who utilized Otter.ai transcription software. TCs' intersectional identities reflect the ways they described themselves in interviews as well as the grade level they will teach.

Figure 1: Political Conocimiento Development Tools

We focus here on the second activity in our suite of tools, the Difficulty Sort, which attends to their comfort with taking risks in teaching to advocate for students. TCs were asked to individually sort into three categories how difficult seven different politically-charged scenarios would be for them to respond to. An example of a scenario is: “The teacher walks past a pair of boys working at a table and overhears one say to the other: ‘Turn on your Asian brain and help me do this problem.’ It’s said loud enough for the entire class to hear.” After sorting their scenarios, the TCs were invited into breakout rooms via Zoom to discuss the ways they sorted the scenarios, noticing similarities and differences, reflecting upon their strengths/missed opportunities in advocating, and considering how their intersectional identities might trigger particular responses from others in the scenario. Then, TCs were asked to reflect on what they learned (“Something that is new for me from this activity is...”) and what questions they have (“Something I’m now wondering about is...”). Finally, TCs were interviewed individually (1–1.5 hours each) about their backgrounds, teaching contexts, and experiences in the activity. We focus on the 49 TCs across our settings.

Following Boyatzis (1998), we created analytic memos on our sessions, giving attention to individual participants and coding general findings for our individual sites. We then met to discuss similarities and differences across our sites and to reflect on the variety of responses from our TCs. We video recorded these research meetings to capture our reflections and deliberations. After our initial meeting analyzing data from the Difficulty Sort, we returned to our data to refine our coding, based upon themes that arose in a given site but were less pronounced across all three sites. For example, in one site, TCs of Color versus white TCs differed in how they made sense of the activity and reflected on how their identities might trigger responses from others. But, upon further exploration, that was not the case in the other two sites. As such, we surfaced the influence of contexts and our TCs identities in the development of PCTM. We report our findings here.

The role of teacher candidates' identities

Most of the teacher candidates found the activity useful for bringing up issues they had not considered but that they will face in their teaching. They also appreciated hearing the views of other people (e.g., to help them note their strengths/challenges and to think about the different ways their peers might approach responding to the scenario). Even so, their identities influenced how they engaged in the session and how they might respond to the scenarios if they were faced with those situations.

Racialized identities

An important aspect of living in the United States is the way people are racialized, and several of the scenarios we crafted included either explicit references to, or coded language about, students of Color. Thus, it is not surprising that we saw concrete differences in the ways that whiteness played out in the activities. For instance, although we offered a specific prompt for breakout room groups to discuss how their identities may have influenced their responses, some white TCs responded that they had not considered their identities before and/or were not sure how the activity helped them further understand their identities. They said things such as, "I am not fully sure, I've never really thought about [my identity]" [white woman, secondary]. This was true even when some of these white TCs were in breakout rooms with TCs of Color who were explicitly discussing their racialized identities, commenting on the ways other people ascribe racial or ethnic identities to them. In this sense, these white TCs' sentiments were race evasive, centering their own white identities as normative. When whiteness was recognized by white TCs, it usually arose as a form of positioning themselves in contrast to or distanced from the students of Color in the scenarios, as if they could not imagine what it would be like to be them. They said such things as:

Who am I to tell them what to think?? I am not a minoritized student. [white woman, secondary]
Sometimes it's tough to speak with students when you're completely, completely different backgrounds. And, I always want to let you know, remind them that I'm here for them [...] I'd love to understand their culture and their, [that's] my thought process. It can be tough to try to connect with those students. [white woman, secondary]

Whiteness also arose as a form of acknowledged authority for responding in the scenarios because they believed others will defer to white people when they take action. In this respect, several of the white teachers were fully aware of their privileged status as it would play out in these scenarios.

I feel that my identity as a cisgender white female will make people listen to me. I am part of a majority and that people hold my identity higher than others. I do not think that it should be that way, but it is. I need to stick up for those that do not have the voice to. [white female TC, elementary]

In these cases, TCs recognized they were positioned in society with white privilege and saw their responsibility to use that privilege to intervene.

At other times, whiteness arose as uneasiness regarding "doing the right thing," which tended to refer less to ensuring justice and more to "not wanting to make a mistake or be seen as racist." They expressed such sentiments as:

Anything with race is difficult as a white person. [white man, secondary]

I'm worried that my good intentions will not be received as such. [white man, secondary]

As a white teacher, I don't want to give anyone the wrong impression." [white woman, elementary]

One scenario depicted a teacher who is giving back student papers and passes by a student with their hand raised and the student exclaims, "Did you see that? She's not helping me because I'm Black!" The white elementary TCs in our study felt more compelled to point out how difficult the situation would be to attend to because of their whiteness, as if they were the victim, not the students in the scenarios. Some worried that they would/could not do the right thing simply because of their white racialized identities.

As a white male I can 'be called anything under the sun' and people would justify it [...] I wouldn't ever meaningfully do that to a student. But once the story gets told [...] and if I don't see the student's hand [...] and I tell them that, but they tell their parents and then they tell someone else [...] I could lose my job. It's just very difficult for me to defend my position because I'm the only teacher in there. It's not like the students can defend me. So [...] it's just difficult for me." [white man, elementary]

In this instance, "anything under the sun" means "being called a racist." Yet, even in attending to his whiteness, he is not able to name race/racism explicitly. He sees his whiteness as leading to an extreme situation – potentially losing his job, which is an unlikely scenario given that most teachers and administrators are white and support other white people, and students hold little status in schools. In feeling this unease, their approach seemed less reflective about what they could do to stand up for students and, instead, TC's expected someone to hand them the correct protocol to follow. This theme was more prominent within the elementary TCs.

Is there a protocol to follow when we realize these educators may cause more harm to children just by being in their classroom? [white woman, elementary]

How do I approach a situation with someone who is in charge of me without being rude or stepping on toes? I normally stand up against people but when I am working for the person it seems like a touchy subject. I know I need to stand up to them but how do I go about that in a nice way? [white man, elementary]

As such, although advocating for students is an explicit goal of the Political Conocimiento Development Tools, getting white teacher candidates to recognize their racialized identities does not guarantee they will acknowledge their white privilege or use it as a springboard to intervene. In fact, as noted here, it could serve as a roadblock to responding.

In contrast to themes that arose among white TCs, most of the secondary TCs of Color were more forthcoming about how their identities could influence how they process the scenarios and how their identity might trigger responses in others. In general, they saw their racialized identities as possible challenges with respect to other adults they might need to confront and as possible strengths with respect to students in the scenarios. Identifying possible negative responses they might get, some TCs expressed:

Identity can trigger some prejudiced thoughts [about me] because I am a minority." [Asian American man, secondary]

[...] if I'm talking to someone who maybe I'm talking to them about [...] bilingual students, if I was talking to them about that textbook thing [a scenario where the school wants to adopt a new textbook that might be harder for multilingual students]. Maybe they would feel like I was attacking how they viewed something just because they're like white, or just because they don't have that experience. Maybe they would think that because I relate to it more, I have like a higher, like I hold myself to a higher ideal than them because I relate to it [...] that could be something that's running through their head that maybe they feel like they're more on the defense, because they don't relate to that as much. [Latina female TC, secondary]

In the first quote, the TC reflects on ways they have experienced prejudice simply because of their racialized identity, a recurring theme for this TC in our sessions. In the second quote, the TC is catering to the comfort of her white colleagues by suggesting that simply being Latina could trigger a defense by others.

On the other hand, in response to a scenario where a teacher overhears two Latinx students discussing how they would have to use their race (as opposed to their grades) to get into college, one TC sees her connection to the students as an asset.

I would be able to maybe share my own experience and how [...] in my college career, and like, I'm here teaching you. So it's possible for you to succeed [...] And I would imagine that, because I have that connection, that we're both Latinx, that they would maybe respect that or like, like that they would understand that perspective that I'm coming from. [Latina female TC, secondary]

For that same scenario, another TC of Color also recognized her identity as a possible strength, but then cautioned against essentializing students.

I did consider trying to connect with them. And the fact that I am a minority as well, but then that conflicts with 'you and I' statements. Just because I'm a minority doesn't mean that I'm going through the exact same thing as another minority." [Palestinian, female TC, secondary]

Because minoritized backgrounds can be seen in multiple ways (a strength or a challenge), simply recognizing one's racialized identity does not necessarily lead to feeling empowered to act. It can serve as a springboard or a roadblock.

The theme of wanting to "Do the right" thing also arose among TCs of Color, but tended to relate to one's ethical identity (e.g., propelling TCs to want to advocate for their students), something we discuss later.

Personality

In addition to racialized identities, self-described personality traits played a role for several of the TCs when considering how they would respond. Although personality can include more self-monitoring aspects than traditional definitions of identity, we include it here because it was explicitly raised by our participants. That is, when asked about their identities, they commented on how being "shy/unsure," a "peace maker," or "the kind of person who speaks their mind" would influence how they respond. Sometimes these personality traits served as a springboard for action, and other times they seemed to serve as roadblocks.

If you ask my friends, they'll say [...] I'm a very opinionated person [...] when I believe in an opinion, it's hard to dissuade me off of it. [Asian American male TC, secondary]

I think it would be hard to first, stand up by yourself because I'm shy, and second, to try to convince a room full of people to agree with an unpopular opinion. [Latina woman, elementary]

The first quote illustrates how identifying as someone who is “opinionated” may serve as a springboard to action, whereas the second quote suggests that being “shy” may serve as a roadblock to advocating for one’s students. Below, we see a TC who begins with the idea that her personality will lead her to address the situation head-on, but then she quickly takes a more cautious tone when considering whether, as a white person, she will be able to do the right thing and intervene on behalf of her students.

I like to be direct and address situations head-on in most cases. If it is something to do with an identity that I don’t personally identify as, however, I struggle a bit with knowing what to do or what would be best because I don’t want to make any mistakes in how I handle the situation.
[white woman, secondary]

In this case, it is unclear if her fear of making a mistake will prevent her from acting, even though she identifies as someone who is “direct,” but it raises the question: How do issues of personality intersect with racialized identities?

We consider that question by considering the following two TCs who share a personality trait but differ in racialized identities.

Maybe it comes from the fact that I’m a middle child in a large family. I often was the peacemaker [...] the person who would come in between two people when they’re fighting and try to get them to understand other perspectives. So, I don’t know how good I am at that, but I do know that that often is my default in certain scenarios. [Palestinian female, secondary]

I do just try to take the stance of like, I’m a very neutral, like, I’m not like, even in all of this, like election stuff, I don’t talk about anything, because I like I just like, I like to make peace not create chaos or anything. [white female TC, secondary]

In these cases, we see that the Palestinian TC who describes herself as a “peace maker” sees that trait as an asset in intervening, whereas the white TC who says she likes to “make peace” seems to use that trait as an excuse not to “create chaos or anything.”

Overall, while self-identified personality traits arose as an expressed variable in both TCs of Color and white TCs, we noted that TCs who, when asked about identity, commented only on the role of their personality and not race/gender (in terms of affecting how they made sense of, or might respond to, the scenarios) tended to be white. Those teacher candidates seemed to use personality in lieu of racialized identities. This interaction between racialized identities and personality traits has piqued our interest and is something we intend to consider further in future analyses.

Grade level

Less prominent were effects of grade level identities on the ways TCs engaged in the activities. We saw some evidence that elementary TCs were less likely to talk about their racialized identities and tended to project a value for Color-evasive teaching. For example, in one site, teacher candidates’ racialized identities were mentioned explicitly in only one of eight breakout groups. When discussing how to respond to a scenario where the Black student accused the teacher of not helping them because of their race, several TCs expressed an interest in pointing out to students that race does not play a factor in the situation. This framing arises in the following group discussion.

You could talk to the student(s) about how maybe you just didn't see the student's hand up and is willing to hear him/her out because everyone's voice is important in her class regardless of race, age, gender, color, hair color, etc [...] you could make it a group discussion to show how things are not about race, age, color, etc in the classroom. [Group, elementary TCs]

As mentioned, several of the TCs talked about how reading and engaging with the scenarios triggered strong feelings. Yet, the elementary TCs, more so than the secondary TCs, tended to focus on the need to regulate those feelings or remain "level headed." However, this distinction was also difficult to parse from identities related to their specific programs and teaching contexts where cooperating teachers might be conveying the preference for this Color-evasive stance. We suspect that because most of the scenarios felt difficult, there was less room for a distinction between the kinds of responses that elementary and secondary TCs might exhibit. Our use with other tools, such as the Similarity Sort (where TCs explore the stories that get told in mathematics and teaching) might show more significant differences between elementary TCs (who tend to focus on loving and caring for young children) versus secondary TCs (who tend to focus on conveying mathematical content).

Mirror test

Elsewhere, Gutiérrez (2015) conceptualized a form of ethical identity for teachers called The Mirror Test, wherein teachers need to be able to look themselves in the mirror and assess whether their actions reflect what they say they stand for. An important part of this stance is identifying to what/whom they hold themselves accountable. Different teachers will have different identities they are trying to uphold, or different Mirror Tests they are trying to pass. Some teachers might focus on fidelity to school mandates/reforms to be seen as a "professional," whereas others might focus on serving their most vulnerable students to be seen as "ethical," or to being seen as a "team player" by colleagues. We saw the Mirror Test as distinguishing between the kinds of reactions that TCs gave. Part of the Mirror Test for many TCs was being student-centered (responding to students' needs, empathizing with them in the scenarios). And, in these cases, TCs felt compelled to advocate. We saw evidence of this attention to students playing out across racialized identities and grade levels.

Teacher candidates who felt the scenarios violated their mirror tests did not always know what to do. But, they felt compelled to *do something*.

I think a lot of the scenarios, in the 'I can do this now' [category], is, I don't know exactly what I would do. But I feel like I wouldn't be able to just listen to that statement and not do anything in the moment. But for this [scenario where a teacher suggests she can rely on her Asian American girls to tutor other students in math], I think I would just, I would just politely phrase to the teacher that, "You know, as teachers, we shouldn't be putting our students in boxes or labeling them [Palestinian female TC, secondary]

One TC described "pulling a Dead Poet's society," referring to a movie about a white teacher in an elite boarding school who gets fired for encouraging his white students to live their lives on their own terms. He clarifies the phrase, saying, "Dead Poet's society is an analogy about engaging students and then getting fired. It's a good movie for teachers to watch." [white man, secondary] This TC seems to be projecting himself as the kind of person

accountable to his students and not the school or administration, so much so that he would get fired for being so student-centered.

Other Mirror Test examples arose as several TCs articulated how they would need to respond because of the kind of teacher they believed themselves to be.

In response to Scenario A [where a student called you out for not helping them because they are Black], I feel like it would just be kind of like really heartbreaking to hear a student say that [...] to think that I'm not presenting myself or the way that I'm teaching is coming off in a way that like I have a prejudice, prejudice against certain students would be really difficult to hear, because then I think I would just have to do a lot of reflection, like personally [...] it's definitely necessary to address that. [Latina female TC, secondary]

[...] we should always word things in a way that we are always on the side of our student, even if the student does something wrong or isn't flourishing as much as we'd want them to. We want students to know that we're on their side and that we're, we're here to support them. Even if the student isn't right in front of us, I feel like that should be our mindset. So I'd want to respond with something that would be in support of our students." [Palestinian female TC, secondary]

Each of the aforementioned TCs were commenting upon how they would hold themselves accountable to students of Color above other things, such as getting along with colleagues or "going with the flow." This sense of solidarity was extended to students who did not share their racialized background (e.g., TC of Color and a white student or a white TC and student of Color). Even so, being student-centered did not necessarily lead to TCs engaging in racial/gender analysis of the scenarios.

[...] it really is so important to stick up for the students in your classroom. I always knew it was the right thing to do, but with the dilemmas that we were given, I realized how important it actually is. [white woman, elementary]

In these cases, TCs saw themselves as accountable to students in a generic category ("all students") versus recognizing that certain students (e.g., students of Color, girls) were being stereotyped or harmed in the scenarios.

Overall, our findings indicate that for the teacher candidates with whom we worked, being highly conscious of their racialized identities, personality traits, grade band focus, and the kind of teacher they want to be served to elicit a range of responses, sometimes leading to a greater inclination to advocate for students (i.e., a springboard for action) and, other times, a hesitation around doing the "correct" thing (i.e., a roadblock to action). We also witnessed interaction effects (e.g., between personality, racialized identities) that demonstrated how a single attribute (e.g., personality) was not the primary predictor of advocating for historically minoritized students. Given the highly context-dependent nature of this work, there is no universal policy we can offer about making TCs aware of specific identities in order to promote advocacy for students. As such, we surfaced tensions in recommendations for future tool design. Should the tools help TCs acknowledge their racialized identities? Should the tools elicit a strong emotional response from TCs? Should the tools be reformatted to include different contexts that might correlate better with grade level focus? These are questions we will continue to grapple with as we move forward.

In this paper, we focused on race/ethnicity and gender identity in relation to TCs' Political Conocimiento in Teaching Mathematics. We found that for TCs who could empathize with students in the scenarios, prompting them to consider their identities might have allowed them to understand why, even if they were not sure of *what* to do, they felt compelled to act in order to reflect an identity they could be proud of. And, TCs who could not easily relate to the students in the scenarios might have used their identities as rationales to avoid intervening. These findings are especially important, as much of the literature on "best practices" in teacher education in the US is normed on white teachers. Future research should continue to investigate the role of these TCs' intersectional identities and also expand to include sexual orientation, religion, linguistic backgrounds, living with a dis/ability, etc. Moreover, further investigation of differences by grade level (elementary or secondary) and contexts (e.g., states that ban Critical Race Theory, teacher education programs with an explicit anti-racist or justice focus) will help the field better understand factors that influence TCs' commitment to take action. Programmatic features may also influence TCs' development of Political Conocimiento in Teaching Mathematics. That is, teacher education programs with an explicit anti-racist or justice focus, including cooperating teachers who share such commitments, may better support TCs to develop PCTM. Finally, TCs should be followed to see how they engage in the suite of tools over time and to document any possible lasting effects of such professional development on their beginning years of teaching.

References

- Association of Mathematics Teacher Educators (2017). *Standards for preparing teachers of mathematics*. Retrieved from <https://amte.net/sites/default/files/SPTM.pdf>
- Aguirre, J. M., Mayfield-Ingram, K., & Martin, D. B. (2013). *The impact of identity in K-8 mathematics: Rethinking equity-based practices*. Reston, VA: National Council of Teachers of Mathematics.
- Boyatzis, R. E. (1998). *Transforming qualitative information: Thematic analysis and code development*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Brown, K. A., (2017). Dispositions of first year teachers who teach mathematics for social justice. *Journal of Multicultural Affairs*, 2(1), 1–9.
- Gonzalez, L. (2009). Teaching mathematics for social justice: Reflections on a community of practice for urban high school mathematics teachers. *Journal of Urban Mathematics Teacher Education*, 2(1), 22–51.
- Gutiérrez, R. (2012). Embracing "Nepantla." Rethinking knowledge and its use in teaching. *Journal of Research in Mathematics Education*, 1(1), 29–56.
- Gutiérrez, R. (2013). Why (urban) mathematics teachers need political knowledge. *Journal of Urban Mathematics Education*, 6(2), 7–19.
- Gutiérrez, R., Gerardo, J. M., Vargas, G. E., & Irving, S. E. (2017). Rehearsing for the politics of teaching mathematics. In S. Kastberg, A. M. Tyminski, A. Lischka, & W. Sanchez, W. (Eds.), *Building support for scholarly practices in mathematics methods* (pp. 149–164). Charlotte, NC: Information Age.
- Holland, D., Lachiotte, W., Jr., Skinner, D., & Cain, C. (2003). *Identity and agency in cultural worlds*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Myers, M., Kokka, K., & Gutiérrez, R. (2021). *It's not a magic pill: How context and identity shape the development of Political Conocimiento*. Selected presentation at the Annual (Virtual) Meeting of the Association of Mathematics Teacher Educators.